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PECULIARITIES OF LEGAL TERMS

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the features of the interpretation of legal terminology. The result of the analysis shows that the author comes to the conclusion about presence of some features of the lexical reflection of the process and results of interpretation in the text of normative legal acts and doctrinal sources. The purpose of this study is to reveal the main problems of studying legal terminology.

Keywords: interpretation, legal regulation, legal term, lexical equivalent, concept, legislation, demand for the term.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЮРИДИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье раскрываются особенности толкования юридической терминологии. Результат анализа показывает, что автор приходит к выводу о наличии некоторых особенностей лексического отражения процесса и результатов толкования в тексте нормативных правовых актов и доктринальных источников. Целью данного исследования является выявление основных проблем изучения юридической терминологии.

Ключевые слова: толкование, правовое регулирование, юридический термин, лексический эквивалент, понятие, законодательство, востребованность термина.

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HUQUQIY ATAMALARNING XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada huquqiy terminologiyani talqin qilish xususiyatlari ochib berilgan. Tahlil natijasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, muallif normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar matni va ta'limot manbalarida sharhlash jarayoni va natijalarini lug'aviy aks ettirishning ayrim xususiyatlari borligi to'g'risida

xulosaga keladi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi yuridik terminologiyani o'rganishning asosiy muammolarini ochib berishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: talqin, huquqiy tartibga solish, yuridik atama, leksik ekvivalent, tushuncha, qonunchilik, atama talabi.

The importance of studying terminology in the modern world is undeniable, on the one hand, terminology is a link between different fields of knowledge, and on the other hand, it contributes to a clear distinction between concepts. In connection with the rapid scientific and technological progress, it seems necessary to pay due attention to the terminological apparatus of various sciences [9]. Terminology does not stand, it is constantly evolving, expanding its boundaries. It is studied by both linguists and terminologists - representatives of the relevant fields of science and technology.

The relevance of the topic of the undertaken research is determined by the fact that legal terminology is considered to be one of the most significant industry term systems. It should be noted that the terminology of law is widely used not only in the professional environment, but also in other areas of language communication, so there is a great demand for learning the language of law for special purposes. Legal terminology is a unique object of study, as it is characterized by a wide variety of areas of application compared to other terminological systems. According to the Commission on the genres of legal texts (Great Britain), the number of types of texts used in the professional field. Such genre diversity is due to the multiplicity of sources of law, and in relation to English legal terminology, and the development of the Anglo-Saxon legal family, which includes, first of all, the legal systems of the United States and Great Britain.

It is rather difficult to conduct a study of systems of legal terms and concepts in English and native language, since one has to deal not so much with the terms themselves, but with different legal systems (as you know, there are deep differences and Anglo-American case law, which manifest themselves, including at the level of terminology). Vocabulary correspondence often does not give a correct idea of a lexical item, since similar terms in two languages have different concepts or a different amount of meaning of concepts that are similar in meaning [12].

The purpose of this study is to reveal the main problems of studying the evolution of legal terminology. The theoretical basis of the study was the works of such scientists as S.S. Alekseev, L.S. Barkhudarov, R.A. Budagov, D.S. Lote, V.M. Leichik, D.I. Miloslavskaya, L.L. Nelyubin, A. Nikinin, A.S. Pigolkin, A.A. Reformatsky, M.A. Reisner, S.P. Khizhnyak, I.O. Chistyakov.

To solve the tasks in this work, the following methods are used:

- study and analysis of texts of laws, normative legal acts, codes;
- comparative analysis of English and American legal terminology;
- theoretical research in the field of linguistics (lexical system of the language);
- study of historical background that influenced the lexical composition of legal terminology.

Abstraction of some legal norms and terms gives rise to the need for cognitive activity, ensuring a correct understanding of legal regulations and their uniformity application. One of the directions of development legal practice is the use of socio-legal experience accumulated in society in the framework of the activities of competent subjects related to the interpretation of law. The purpose of such activity is to establish the content of legal norms, to clarify the meaning of the normative prescription, its place in the system of legal regulation. Wherein should take into account the historical situation of the period of development and adoption of legal

act, its purpose and direction, consequences of implementation, etc. [1]. The need to establish the real (genuine) content of legal terminology is explained by the fact that "conceptual and terminological uncertainty leads to contradictions in the system of legislation, interpretations by passing the law, arbitrary application of legislative norms" [2].

With regard to legal terminology, in most cases the focus is researchers are not all existing interpretations. It is about doctrinal and official interpretation [3], about normative and scientific [4]. By this reason for the development of legal and linguo-legal ways of searching for the meaning of special terms included in the language of law, does not lose theoretical relevance and has practical significance in connection with the fact that "the rejection of strict, at the level of concepts,

interpretation of the law and its terms in the judicial practice is tantamount to a rejection of precision not only in its understanding, but also in its application [5].

Today, in the theory of law and the state, a legal term is understood as “a word (or phrase) that is used in legislation, is generalized name of a legal concept that has an exact and definite meaning, and is distinguished by semantic unambiguity, functional stability” [6]. However, on practice, such a sign of a term as semantic unambiguity is not always expressed sufficiently. This situation necessitates the establishment of semantic features of such seemingly well-known terms as “the text of the document”, for example, in the case of determining the bill of exchange legal meaning of special items [7, 5]. In general, the legal literature often talks about the need to interpret numerous terms that are widely used in various branches of private and public law such as "advertising" [8], “substantial violation of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens or organizations or legally protected interests of society or the state” [9], “court” [10], "justice" [11], etc.

The ambiguity of the term is usually explained by the inaccuracy of the choice of the lexical equivalent, incompatibility of terms, incorrect choice of the term in terms of its stylistic affiliation [12]. The term "interpretation" is not found not only in the text of normative legal acts, but also in scientific publications, where authors often single it out with quotation marks as a referent of a state widely known in theory and law concepts. So, for example, O.V. Karpeev explores the features of civil law, regulation of transportation, notes: “the term organization of various modes of transport”. Obviously, the common use that the term "interpretation" finds in legislation and doctrinal sources to designate a semantic search procedure, suggests the presence of some features of its use in the text of normative legal acts and doctrinal sources.

Firstly, the term "interpretation" is traditionally used in a special legal language in relation to the vocabulary of normative legal acts and agreements to determine:

- the order of interaction between the participants in the legal relationship [14];
- the price of the contract [15];
- terms of the contract [11];
- the objective side
- criminal act [7,8], etc.

Such cases, analysis of the features of the terminological reference of a legal concept allows define the limits of its scope and the possibility of its application for the legal assessment of public relations.

Secondly, interpretation is understood as process and the result of establishing the actual content of the rules of law in order to their correct implementation [1]. When customs in the field of foreign economic relations in a number of cases are interpreted by international organizations [8], we are talking about interpretation as process, and when “a broad interpretation of the term “electronic means of payment”, “On the national payment system” raises many questions from credit institutions” [9], meaning interpretation in the interpretation as a result.

Thirdly, it should be noted that in various regulatory documents we can talk not only about the interpretation of legal, but also other special terminology [10]. Besides, in some normative legal acts mention the interpretation of such types of terms that are rarely found in legal texts as “periodic” [12]. This is indicated that interpretation in the process of lawmaking and law enforcement subjected not only to legal, but also to other terminology, as well as a very extensive area of application of the term "interpretation" associated with legal vocabulary and special languages of other areas of knowledge.

Fourthly, in legal science there are errors in the choice of the subject of interpretation. There is an error in the subject interpretation that ignores the authors of the linguistic connection between the concept and term. Due to the fact that the term is used in legislation as a generalized name for a legal concept [6], the latter cannot be part of legal terminology.

Fifthly, the use of the word “interpretation” itself in the text of a normative legal act is not always consistent with its structure and appointment. Procedure for registration and registration investment agreements concluded in relation to owned real estate objects, additional agreements on

termination to them, protocols for the preliminary distribution of residential (non-residential) space, acts on the results of (partial) implementation of investment projects [14].

In legal texts, one can find the words "explanation", "clarification", "interpretation", which are used as synonyms for the term "interpretation" [2,9]. The similarity of this terminology may give the impression that it is possible to develop standard approaches to the interpretation of terms and categories. However, this possibility is nothing more than an illusion due to the inherent nature of each term used as a synonym for the word "interpretation", own semantic shades. In addition, some authors discover very original synonyms of "interpretation", which does not always add semantic certainty to this term. So, G.O. Abolonin considers the features of the theoretical understanding of the civil process, indicates that "the term "jurisdiction" comes from the Latin words "juris" - "law" and "dicere" - "to say" that means the power to interpret the law and announce the conclusions" [10]. In this regard, further promising may be a wider use of the term "interpretation", which is still in its early stages of development. jurisprudence has proven its effectiveness in the field of process and result description with establishing the content of the rules of law in order to properly implement them. In the legal world, every term changes, we need to learn to distinguish certain words from others, because a single term can be decisive in a legal tradition. Community interpreters are very careful to be able to change the whole context of the situation each time they do the work in their hands.

For a clearer description of legal terminological systems, it is necessary to develop a classification of terms in this subject area, and therefore, it becomes necessary to choose classification grounds. One of these grounds may be the factor of belonging of a word to a sublanguage of a certain field of activity. Let us dwell in more detail on the previously developed classifications of legal terminology. The classification was developed by A.S. Pigolkin [9,10], it is carried out according to vertical and horizontal principles. At the top of the vertical classification will be the terminology enshrined in the Basic Law and other legislative acts, that is, general legal terminology, which combines terms used in all branches of law and denotes the broadest concepts. Horizontal terminology covers various types of intersectoral and sectoral term systems. Cross-sectoral terminology is the terms used in several branches of law ("material liability", "significant damage", "misconduct", etc.). The main volume of legal terms falls on interbranch terminology, while the number of industry terms is relatively small.

We find a slightly different classification in D.I. Miloslavskaya, who distinguishes the following groups of terms:

- commonly used;
- commonly used, having a narrower, special meaning in a normative act;
- purely legal;
- technical.

Like any other sphere of public life, jurisprudence cannot do without special terminology, which is specially developed by the legislator to regulate public relations. Special legal terms, as a rule, succinctly and relatively accurately denote the concept used in jurisprudence ("plaintiff", "conviction", "forfeit", "inquiry", etc.). However, their number is not so great, but, despite this, they are quite often used in various documents of a legal nature. They are used to denote special concepts and only in jurisprudence. There are many such special legal terms in business documents and legislative texts, the meaning of which cannot always be explained solely from linguistic positions, for example, the term "legal entity". Indeed, in the literal sense, the word "person" refers to a person, and not to any organization, association. However, the use of such terms is justified, because from the point of view of their practical conventional use, they have advantages, unambiguously defining specific legal concepts.

Many terms that were created by the legislator and were originally purely legal, later became widespread in everyday life, in fiction, and are actively used outside of jurisprudence ("criminal", "law", "alimony", etc.). They ceased to be properly legal, they turned into ordinary ones. In legal documentation, many terms are used, borrowed from various fields of science, technology, art, as well as professionalism. In the literature, the name "technical terms" was assigned to them (for

example, “diapositive”, “microfarad”, “phonogram”). In the process of applying the rules of law in various spheres of public life, it is often impossible to do without special technical terms. It is necessary to adhere to the rule that technical terms are used in the sense that is assigned to them in the relevant branch of knowledge.

Special legal and technical terms are very convenient: they unambiguously designate the necessary concept, contribute to a clearer presentation of regulatory requirements, thereby contributing to a more correct understanding and application of the latter. In other words, they condense verbal information as much as possible, save the means of conveying legislative thought. With the help of such terms, unambiguity, semantic specificity, and completeness of legal formulations can be achieved. It is hardly advisable to replace special terms with detailed descriptive expressions, since this would lead to the cumbersomeness of regulations, business documents, and would make their application difficult. Of course, special terms should be used within the limits of semantic and informational necessity, without overloading documents with them. For example, the use of such terms is appropriate in normative acts for special purposes, for a limited circle of specialists, and inappropriate in acts that are designed for a wide range of citizens.

Of course, special terms should be used within the limits of semantic and informational necessity, without overloading documents with them. For example, the use of such terms is appropriate in normative acts for special purposes, for a limited circle of specialists, and inappropriate in acts that are designed for a wide range of citizens. There is also a similar division in the legal literature, in which three types of legal terms are distinguished:

- commonly used terms that are used in everyday speech and are understood by everyone;
- special legal terms that have a special legal content (“letter of credit”, “statement of claim”, etc.). Such terms serve to designate legal concepts, express legal constructions, industry typification, etc.;
- special-technical legal terms that reflect the area of special knowledge, for example, safety regulations, equipment maintenance, expertise of technical solutions, etc.

However, commonly using terms can also become legal. In order to make special legal terms understandable to all subjects of legal relations, the legislator uses norms that do not directly regulate social relations, but reveal the content of any legal terms. Such norms are called norm-definitions. The effectiveness of legal terms depends on how the legislator fulfills a number of rules for legal terminology. Let us turn to the fundamental study “Legal Terminology: Formation and Composition” by S.P. Khizhnyak, which gives a classification of features that lawyers apply to the term. According to the author, the term should be:

- unified, that is, used in this law or other normative act in the same sense, to be unambiguous within one system;
- generally recognized, and not invented by the legislator only for this case, it is unacceptable to use the term in some special sense;
- stable, that is, the meaning and meaning of the term should not change depending on the context;
- logically related to other terms of this system;
- correlated with the professional sphere of usage.

In conclusion, the division of legal acts into normative legal, law enforcement and interpretive acts existing in the legal doctrine and from the need to take into account the existence of terms developed and used by legal science that have not been used in legal acts, but which also relate to legal terminology. Nevertheless, attention should be paid to the fact that this division is largely conditional due to the fact that in practice it is very difficult to distinguish between these types of legal terminology. This is due to the fact that the terms of both normative legal acts and legal science are used in law enforcement and interpretive acts, as well as in the development of normative legal acts, all types of legal terminology are used. It is believed that for the convenience of analysis, legal vocabulary can be divided into classes according to the method of nominating a concept (terms, termonyms, professionalisms). Having considered the theoretical prerequisites for the study of terminology in general, and legal terminology in particular, we can draw the following conclusions:

- There are many definitions of the term "term" given by different scientists, but they all agree that, ideally, the term should be short, monosemantic, devoid of expression, although in practice it is very difficult to achieve these conditions.
- The main law of the state - the Constitution - is the source of fundamental legal terms. Using them, the state, represented by its authorities, speaks the language of law and expresses its will: it cancels and changes the norms; establishes new rules of conduct; reinforces existing social relationships.
- Any division of legal terminology is largely conditional due to the fact that in practice it is very difficult to draw a clear line between the terms and bring them under some specific classification grounds.

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